

The information-seeking behavior of emergency physicians under the pressure and uncertainty of a crisis

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

Our contribution aims to present one of the first studies conducted in the field of information sciences among emergency physicians during a Covid-19 crisis in France. This research project was carried out without funding. It was conducted entirely through the generous cooperation of emergency physicians. The presentation will focus on the information seeking behavior of emergency physicians of one of the four medical emergency aid services of Paris and its three neighboring administrative departments. More precisely, we focus on information access (online and offline) and the information sources of these actors. In addition to sharing our findings, this communication offers insights into the French experience during this global crisis. We also reflect on how information seeking and sharing could be improved in crisis situations.

Value of the contribution

Many researchers have been interested in the information behavior of health professionals, but studies focusing on emergency physicians, and more specifically during a crisis, are less common. Our contribution provides novel insights about the information seeking behavior of key actors within the French medical emergency care system during the Covid-19 crisis. For doctors, information and information sources are some of their most important resources, “essential to contribute to the provision of quality care to patients” (Letang & Espitia, 2019).

In France, emergency physicians are trained as general practitioners and then specialize in emergency medicine. This specialty was officially recognized in 2015. Emergency physicians in emergency services called SAMU are front-line actors who

take care of patients whose state of health is compromised. Their role is to ensure the survival of patients in their care until they are transferred to hospital. This study underscores the challenges emergency physicians face in their everyday work, particularly with respect to decision-making during crisis situations. We will begin with some general observations about information behavior of emergency physicians experienced through the *darkness* and *light* of a crisis. Afterwards, we will present the findings of our study regarding how emergency physicians access information and what information sources they relied on during the Covid-19 crisis. Our findings stem from our interviews with emergency physicians about their information activity at the height of the pandemic. The results of our study point to ways that directives, policies and procedures in the health sector could be improved.

Research outline

This contribution is built on a qualitative study conducted during the Covid-19 health crisis in France. Striking in March 2020, the crisis resulted in over eight months of restrictions and various sanitary measures. The study aims to explore the information seeking behavior of emergency physicians, working in the emergency medical service in Paris, during emergency and crisis situations. In France, the emergency medical services found themselves on the front line responding to the pandemic, managing, among other health emergencies, the flow of Covid-19 patients.

In this study we use the sense-making methodology and grounded theory to collect data through nineteen interviews and observations *in situ*. The collected data (24 hours of observation and more than 13 hours of recordings) was gathered and analyzed using the NVivo qualitative data analysis software. The coding phase was carried out according to emerging concepts from our data. Our method involved assigning meaningful labels to units of discourse within each interview. The coded units are then regrouped and reunited under emerging concepts. This is a progressive and iterative process and act of conceptualization.

In a time of crisis, the metaphor of “darkness” can be associated with a lack of (reliable) information, time pressures for action, a lack of sense, etc. Characterized as a period of increased information and uncertainty, the crisis renders decision-making more difficult. In this communication we will present findings from our study framed within the context of the conference theme. We will focus on information access (online and

offline), information sources used by emergency physicians, and difficulties encountered by these actors during a crisis.

Understanding how emergency physicians find and use crucial information, what their information needs are during a crisis, what information gaps they confront, what difficulties they face, etc., is crucial for ensuring effective responses and patient care. By shedding light on their information behavior, we can ultimately provide healthcare professionals with better guidance on how to identify reliable and timely information and to navigate through crisis situations with confidence and efficiency. Our study's findings can inform the development of improved medical information management strategies within healthcare institutions. This, in turn, can facilitate better coordination of actions, decision-making, and information sharing among healthcare professionals. In particular, we propose updating professional documentation in order to consider the needs of emergency physicians regarding information and information sources, both in general as well as specifically during crises.

While this empirical research offers valuable insights, it is limited by the sample size. To broaden the generalizability of our findings, future studies should include a larger and more diverse participant pool. Additionally, investigating information behavior in the context of other emergency medical services and crisis situations would strengthen the conclusions and potentially reveal broader patterns.

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